

EOSC WITHIN NATIONAL STRATEGIES FOR DIGITAL SKILLS

Recommendations' Report

Date of Publication: 15/12/2020

Author: LDK SA

Executive Summary

The report is targeting at providing a list for recommendations for various types of policy makers (including EOSC stakeholders) with the purpose of providing well-rounded, all-inclusive (research-government-industry-public) options to include into national strategies for Digital Skills and upskilling. The framework, within which the recommendations were deployed, considered:

- The COVID-19 pandemic and the rapid changes in the digital transformation of key areas, science and research included, revealing the role of data: FAIRness and OPENness, Artificial Intelligence expansion, Data Science, e-infrastructures, e-services, interoperability (technical-human), digital skills for all. This is much more relate to the development of the competent human capital to practice and facilitate EOSC Open Science principles;
- EOSC digital skills ecosystem and the skills' needs associated to run and use data for research (Researchers, ICT professionals, Libraries & Information Scientists);
- EOSC training infrastructure components: organisation, processes, content, resources (human and technical)
- The key thematic areas (building blocks) for HR development and upskilling: People & Actors, Policies, Governance & Processes, Technology & Learning Environments and their translation into the assessed complexity of the EOSC ecosystem regarding the digital upskilling for researchers:

The analysis has also considered the landscape analysis of 9 EU MS/AC: DN, FI, FR, GR, HU, LT, NL, PT, CH, the resulting GAP Analysis, and an EOSC Consultation for the validation of the gaps and of the initially identified actions to be taken to tackle them.

The **eleven (11) key recommendations** developed on the basis of the previous analysis are presented below:

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This Study has been funded by the EOSCsecretariat.eu which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Programme call H2020-INFRAEOSC-2018-4, Grant Agreement number 831644

The above recommendations can also be categorised according to the four key thematic areas: Policies, People and Actors, Governance/Processes, Technology and Infrastructure:

Finally, for each key recommendation a detailed analysis is provided, comprising references related to: the association of the recommendation to the SRIA Priorities for Skills & Training, the identification of specific action needed for its implementation, the expected outputs, the stakeholders that need to be involved, as well as the shared costs & the potential sources of funding.

